

Distorted accountability: Social media use, disinformation, and the erosion of political trustworthiness

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Abstract

This article investigates how social media use and elite-driven disinformation impact citizens' ability to make rational judgments about political trustworthiness. Drawing on data from three Eurobarometer waves (2021–2023) across all 27 EU member states and paired with macro-level governance indicators, we distinguish between political trust and trustworthiness, the latter conceptualized as alignment between public trust and objective institutional performance. We categorize respondents into four trust types of judgments on political trust: skeptical trust, skeptical mistrust, credulous trust, and cynical mistrust. Subsequently, we examine how traditional media and social media use influences these judgments. Results show that frequent social media use is associated with higher probability of irrational judgments. This association appears stronger in environments where political elites use social media to disseminate disinformation or hate speech. These findings challenge the optimistic assumptions of the “virtuous circle” thesis in the digital context and highlight the polarizing influence of algorithm-driven and elite-manipulated online environments.

Keywords

Political trust; trustworthiness; social media; disinformation; political communication

Introduction

The rise of new social and alternative media raises critical questions about their ultimate impact on democracy. Independent media can fulfil an essential public service by disseminating information on current events and political issues, thereby keeping citizens informed. Scholars have extensively analyzed the role of legacy and social media in shaping citizens' trust in democratic systems and political institutions through mechanisms such as information provision, priming, and framing (Ottati, Wilson, and Lambert, 2016; Citrin and Stoker, 2018; Kananovich, 2022).

Political trust, commonly defined as citizens' confidence in the integrity, competence, and fairness of political actors and institutions, has long been a central focus in political science (Barber, 1983; Rose-Ackerman, 2001; Seyd, 2024). However, there is a pressing need to shift this focus toward examining political trustworthiness. Unlike political trust, which reflects a subjective perception, political trustworthiness is an objective measure. It assesses whether political institutions and leaders genuinely act in a manner that merits public trust. This concept encompasses the ethical and competent fulfilment of fiduciary responsibilities by those in power, with trustworthy authorities expected to demonstrate integrity, fairness, and efficiency. By prioritizing trustworthiness, scholars can gain deeper insights into the mechanisms underlying democratic accountability. This perspective challenges the assumption that trust is inherently beneficial and underscores the risks of "over-trusting" corrupt or incompetent leaders.

Trustworthiness emphasizes the principal-agent relationship and judgments assessing whether leaders and institutions fulfil their obligations to act in the interest of their clients. Trustworthiness is monitored by performance indices. This approach distinguishes between rational trust and mistrust, which strengthens accountability, and affective trust and mistrust (credulous trust and cynical mistrust), which may erode institutional integrity (Norris, 2022; Levi and Stoker, 2000). It aligns with democratic principles that advocate for critical citizenship and informed scrutiny of leaders (Norris, 2000; Cappella and Jamieson, 1997).

The cognitive predispositions of individuals, as well as the media environment in which they operate, are central to forming judgments of political trustworthiness. Media environments not only provide critical information but also act as filters that shape the context in which citizens evaluate political actors and institutions (Norris, 2024). Recently, scholarly attention has expanded to include social media, examining how online networks and evolving norms of political communication influence public perceptions and the dual processes of building or eroding political trust (Zhou et al., 2020; Jimoh et al., 2024).

This article contributes to the current scholarship in the following ways. The major contribution is in the investigation of the social media use influence on the judgments of trustworthiness. Specifically, we examine whether the intensity of social media use impacts the accuracy of perceptions whether national political institutions are trustworthy. Second contribution is that our analysis includes the interaction between social media use and disinformation environments, specifically the political elite's use of social media to spread disinformation and political hate speech. This way we can isolate social media's impact on rational judgment on the one hand, and how elite disinformation reinforces that effect on the other hand. Third, it operationalizes trustworthiness quantitatively by estimating the divergence between citizens' trust levels and performance-based expectations, using multilevel models across 27 EU countries.

This study examines public political trust using individual-level data from three waves of the Eurobarometer (2021–2023). The analysis covers all 27 EU member states, with country-level

indicators drawn from Eurostat, the Varieties of Democracy project, and the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. Trustworthiness is operationalized following Van der Meer and Van Erkel (2023) and Norris (2024) as the residual error in multilevel regression models predicting public trust based on governance performance indices.

Drawing on existing research, we develop an analytical framework that conceptualizes the mechanisms through which social media impacts trust judgments. The findings suggest a negative association between social media use and the probability of making a rational judgment on trust. More intensive social media use is linked to a lower likelihood of such judgment of trust and subsequently will move away to either skeptical mistrust or credulous trust. This is underlined by the impact of the social media content and the extent to which political elite (ab)uses social media to spread disinformation and hate speech. In countries where political elite spread disinformation on social media, respondents show lower probability of making a rational judgment on political trust. Thus, the impact of political elite abusing social media is re-enforcing the social media use as such. These dynamics underscore the role of social media in shaping democratic accountability and public trustworthiness.

Political trustworthiness

In Western societies, the traditional focus on political trust often assumes its inherent value for democracy, linking high levels of trust to civic engagement, regime legitimacy, and voluntary compliance with government policies (e.g., paying taxes, adhering to laws). Scholars like Crozier, Huntington and Watanuki (1975) consider political trust in government to be an imperative prerequisite for democratic rule and institutional integrity. This perspective can obscure critical distinctions, however, between public trust and the performance that justifies it—namely, trustworthiness.

Trust, as it is commonly measured, is an inherently subjective attitude influenced by citizens' perceptions and cognitive biases, which may not always align with objective indicators of political performance. For instance, high trust in corrupt or incompetent governments ("credulous trust") may mask systemic failures, while low trust in well-functioning institutions ("cynical mistrust") can undermine democratic stability. Thus, reliance on trust alone can lead to misleading conclusions about the health of democratic systems (Norris, 2000; Van der Meer, 2018).

Trustworthiness, by contrast, shifts the analytical focus from citizens' perceptions to the qualities and performance of political actors and institutions. It represents the degree to which the workings of political authorities meet normative benchmarks of integrity, competence, responsiveness, and fairness (Miller and Listhaug, 1990; Citrin and Stoker, 2018). Norris defines trustworthiness as "informal social contract where principals authorize agents to act on their behalf in the expectation that the agent will fulfil their responsibilities with competency, integrity, and impartiality despite conditions of risk and uncertainty" (2022, p.4). This way trustworthiness provides a more rigorous evaluative framework than trust alone, as it requires an examination whether trust is warranted, reflecting an alignment between institutional performance and public expectations.

Norris (2024) further highlights that trustworthiness should be seen as an ethical obligation of political authorities to act competently, impartially, and in the public interest. This perspective reinforces the role of trustworthiness in fostering informed citizen judgments and enhancing electoral accountability. Without this focus, political trust can become a heuristic prone to manipulation by misinformation, populist appeals, or partisan biases. For example, consider a country where the government downplayed risks, spread misinformation, and made decisions based on political gain

rather than public well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite this, many citizens continued to trust the government due to partisan loyalty or populist rhetoric rather than an objective assessment of trustworthiness. In such a case, trust functions as a mere heuristic, making it vulnerable to manipulation and ultimately undermining democracy. For trust to be grounded in genuine trustworthiness, it should be based on informed judgments and electoral accountability, reflecting the government's implementation of effective public health measures.

Building on Norris (2022), we distinguish four types of political trustworthiness based on the alignment between citizens' expressed trust in political institutions and the trust levels predicted by the objectively measured performance indicators. Skeptical trust and skeptical mistrust occur when citizens' judgments are (relatively) congruent with objective performance. In the case of skeptical trust, citizens are willing to support institutions that demonstrate competence, integrity, and impartiality, but they remain attentive to performance and willing to revise their evaluations when evidence suggests misconduct or failure. This is not blind faith - rather, it is a form of monitoring trust (Levi and Stoker, 2000) that combines confidence with vigilance. Van der Meer (2010; 2017) frames this as trust grounded in rational evaluations of institutional performance. Skeptical mistrust, by contrast, arises when citizens accurately perceive those institutions as underperforming and make an informed, evidence-aligned decision not to place confidence in political actors.

In contrast, credulous trust and cynical mistrust represent a mismatch between subjective trust and objective performance. Credulous trust arises when citizens considerably overestimate institutional trustworthiness despite poor performance, whereas cynical mistrust occurs when citizens underestimate trustworthiness despite positive performance. These mismatched judgments are more likely to be driven by biases, incomplete information, or flawed reasoning, and thus diverge from a rational assessment of government performance.

We set skeptical trust as the reference category in our statistical models because from a normative democratic perspective, skeptical trust represents the most desirable stance among the four types of political trustworthiness because it combines confidence in institutions with critical vigilance (Norris, 2011; 2024; Levi and Stoker, 2000). Citizens with skeptical trust believe institutions are performing well and legitimate, but they also retain a readiness to withdraw trust if evidence of misconduct or failure emerges. This stance supports both democratic legitimacy and accountability, as it sustains cooperation, law abidance, and engagement in collective problem-solving (Anderson et al., 2005; Marien and Hooghe, 2011) while avoiding the complacency of unconditional trust.

By contrast, skeptical mistrust, although also grounded in relatively accurate performance assessments, reflects an environment in which institutions are failing to meet citizens' expectations. While this can motivate reform, persistent skeptical mistrust can erode system legitimacy, weaken compliance, and reduce cooperation (van der Meer, 2010; Norris, 2011). Therefore, skeptical mistrust represents a reactive stance to institutional underperformance, not an optimal state for democratic functioning.

In the Norris model of trustworthiness, the media serve as a crucial intermediary connecting citizens with political authorities. Historically, traditional independent media sources, such as newspapers, television, and radio, have played a central role in informing the public about governance processes, policy decisions, and political actors. By striving to provide accurate and balanced information, these outlets have been regarded as necessary—but not sufficient—conditions for enabling citizens to form rational evaluations of trustworthiness based on evidence rather than emotion alone (Norris, 2000). However, the role of legacy media has increasingly been called into question due to their complex and sometimes ambiguous relationship with political and economic

power structures at both national and international levels. This entanglement raises legitimate concerns about their reliability and, moreover, currently questions about their importance compared to other sources of information.

Social media platforms have introduced another, rather complex layer to the media's role in trustworthiness judgement process. Those like Facebook, X, Instagram and TikTok enable widespread and instantaneous information sharing, which can enhance political awareness. However, these platforms are also prone to the rapid dissemination of misinformation and disinformation, complicating citizens' ability to evaluate trustworthiness accurately. Algorithms that prioritize sensationalist or polarizing content can amplify biases, creating echo chambers that skew public perceptions of political performance (Schuck, 2017).

Empirical research suggests that individuals who consume news from traditional media outlets, such as television and reputable news websites, generally exhibit higher levels of political trust (Brosius, van Elsas and de Vreese, 2019; Norris, 2000; Karlsen and Aalberg, 2023). This phenomenon has been attributed to the structured and professional nature of traditional journalism, which typically adheres to established norms of credibility, accuracy, and accountability (Ceron and Memoli, 2015).

By contrast, the dynamics of social media may contribute to diminished perceptions of political trustworthiness. The decentralized and largely unregulated nature of social media platforms could facilitate the rapid dissemination of misinformation, disinformation, and sensationalist content. These characteristics might, in turn, erode trust in political actors and institutions, potentially fostering skepticism and political cynicism (Majerczak and Strzelecki, 2022).

Trustworthiness and social media

The media malaise theory (Robinson, 1976) has long been a cornerstone of political communication scholarship, positing that exposure to negative political content fosters cynicism and distrust among the public. Historically, empirical studies suggested that traditional mass media, particularly television, by sustained exposure to conflict and negativity diminished trust in political institutions and actors. Over the years, the media malaise theory has faced substantial criticism. Norris's (2000) virtuous circle thesis offered a counterargument, asserting that in democratic societies, news media often play a constructive role in fostering political trust, civic engagement, and political knowledge. This thesis emphasized that, particularly in open media environments with robust public service broadcasters, balanced and educational coverage enables citizens to make informed evaluations of governance and political processes.

As social media platforms such as Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), and TikTok have become dominant sources of news and political information (Newman et al., 2024), concerns about their effects on perceptions of political trustworthiness have intensified. The ability of social media to amplify sensationalist narratives and misinformation has raised alarm over its potentially detrimental impact on public trust in political actors and institutions. A systematic review by Lorenz-Spreen et al. (2023) on digital media and democracy found that most studies identifying causal effects suggest predominantly negative consequences of digital media on political trust. Consequently, initial expectations that social media would foster deliberative democracy (Boulianne, 2015) and promote more tolerant democratic attitudes through deliberative practices (Holst and Moe, 2021) have increasingly been counterbalanced by concerns about its broader impact on democracy and political trust, in particular. The next section explores in greater detail the mechanisms that may shape the relationship between social media exposure and political trust.

The existing literature identifies several mechanisms inherent to how social media affect citizens' evaluations of political information and, by extension, political trustworthiness. These mechanisms include algorithmic curation, selective exposure, and the echo chamber effect, as well as challenges related to content curation.

Social media platforms are thought to utilize *algorithms* that prioritize content based on user engagement metrics such as likes, shares, and comments. While this may enhance user interaction, it could also amplify sensationalist and partisan content. Consequently, users might be disproportionately exposed to information that aligns with their pre-existing beliefs, potentially shaping their perceptions of political trustworthiness. This algorithm-driven content curation may contribute to the formation of "filter bubbles" (Pariser, 2011), which could isolate users from diverse perspectives and limit their capacity for balanced evaluations of political actors and institutions. Citizens become increasingly reliant on ideologically congruent yet incomplete information. This is one of the potential mechanisms how intense use of social media may lower the ability of citizens make rational, informed judgments of trust.

Social media could also foster communities where like-minded individuals dominate discourse, creating *echo chambers* that help reinforce prevailing narratives and marginalize dissenting opinions (Burns, 2021; Sunstein, 2001). In an echo chamber, users are continuously exposed to narratives that confirm their ideological stance while filtering out dissenting viewpoints. If these narratives emphasize corruption, incompetence, or bias within political institutions, individuals may develop heightened skepticism or even outright distrust toward governments or other political institutions. Over time, this erosion of institutional trust can weaken perceived legitimacy, fostering political cynicism, disengagement, or even support for radical alternatives.

Conversely, if an echo chamber consistently portrays political institutions in a positive light, trust may become artificially inflated, shielding these institutions from legitimate scrutiny. This can create a form of *credulous trust*, where individuals overlook governance failures due to a distorted, overly favorable media environment.

Both filter bubbles and echo chambers distort the information environment, reducing citizens' ability to evaluate political institutions based on objective governance performance. Those locked in *anti-government echo chambers* may reject legitimate institutional efforts, even when policies are effective. Meanwhile, those in *pro-government echo chambers* may ignore governance failures, reinforcing an uncritical, credulous trust that weakens democratic accountability. In both cases, the result is the absence of rational judgments of trust based on objective performance of institutions with potentially negative consequences for democratic accountability.

Factors as echo chambers and filter bubbles collectively suggest that as individuals increasingly rely on social media for political information, they might become isolated from objective and diverse news and thus lose the ability to evaluate the political trustworthiness rationally.

Our first set of hypotheses thus posits that *higher intensity of social media use will be associated with a greater likelihood of credulous trust (H1a), and a greater likelihood of cynical mistrust (H1b), relative to skeptical trust.*

Next to algorithms, the professional supervision of content is thought to be also influential. Traditional media outlets typically rely on professional editorial oversight to ensure the accuracy and coherence of their reporting. In contrast, social media is dominated by user-generated content, ranging from citizen journalism to opinion pieces. While this potentially democratizes the flow of information, it also could facilitate the spread of unverified and biased narratives. The absence of rigorous fact-checking and editorial standards on social media platforms may further complicate

citizens' ability to evaluate political trustworthiness accurately. Misinformation and disinformation thrive in an online environment, as these types of content are often shared more widely than factual news (Majerczak and Strzelecki, 2022). It is well documented that social media is increasingly leveraged for coordinated information operations (Mechkova et al. 2024). Governments, political parties and other actors aim to manipulate public discourse in line with their interests, exploiting social media's vast reach. This way, the perception of institutions' performance may become less rational and more influenced by the unverified and emotionally colored content produced by political elite. In other words, the political elite's use of social media to spread disinformation may drive the ability of public to judge the trustworthiness of political authorities away from the factual, objective performance-based criteria.

Thus, our second hypothesis (H2) reads as follows: *Higher intensity of political elite's disinformation will increase the probability of citizens mismatched judgments of political trust (credulous trust or cynical mistrust) rather than accurate judgments.*

Traditional media and social media seem to play distinct roles in providing accurate and objective information necessary for informed political judgments. While traditional media has long been regarded as a more reliable source due to professional standards like fact-checking and editorial oversight (Cavaliere 2020), the social media are rather prone to misinformation due to their decentralized nature and reliance on user-generated content. Algorithms prioritize sensational and emotionally engaging content, which often distorts political realities and leads to the rapid spread of falsehoods (Lazer et al., 2018). Studies have shown that misinformation spreads faster on social media than the truth, contributing to the polarization of political views (Vosoughi et al., 2018). Social media, while fostering engagement and participation, often undermines informed decision-making through the rapid spread of misinformation and algorithmic biases, ultimately hindering users' ability to make rational political judgments. Our third hypothesis (H3) thus states that *traditional news media will be associated with a higher probability of making accurate judgments of political trust (skeptical trust) compared to reliance on social media.*

Concepts, methods, and data

As already stated, we follow Van der Meer and Van Erkel (2023) and Norris (2024) approach to political trustworthiness. Thus, in the first step, we estimated multilevel logistic regression model using repeated cross-national, longitudinal dataset. We needed this first step to calculate the expected value of trust based on the objective performance of the countries. Subsequently we estimated the regression residuals, which are basically the individual differences between the expected and measured trust levels. We used the residuals to construct four categories of trust.

This operationalization captures two dimensions. The direction of the residuals distinguishes *type*: positive residuals indicate that observed trust level exceeds performance-based expectations, while negative residuals indicate the measured trust falling short of expectations (i.e. mistrust). The magnitude of the residuals reflects the degree of trust or mistrust. Thus, our measurement framework not only captures whether judgments are accurate or mismatched but also differentiates between credulous and cynical forms of inaccuracy, consistent with the two-dimensional typology proposed by Norris (2022). For detailed description of the multilevel logistic regression we employed for estimating the residuals, including results, see Appendix 1.

Political trust is analyzed using data from the Eurobarometer. The study encompasses all 27 European Union member states, representing diverse media systems, historical legacies, contemporary regimes, and cultural traditions. The Eurobarometer features a standardized set of

questions measuring political trust in various institutions on a binary scale (tend to trust vs. not tend to trust). Although the Eurobarometer collects data on trust in multiple institutions (e.g., the national parliament, the European Parliament, the legal system, the police, politicians, and the United Nations), this study follows the approach by Van Erkel and Van der Meer (2016) and Van der Meer and Van Erkel (2023). Consistent with their methodology, we focus on two items: 'Do you tend to trust or not tend to trust the national government?' and 'Do you tend to trust or not tend to trust the national parliament?' As these questions are originally binary in the Eurobarometer questionnaire, we decided to follow the approach by Van der Meer and van Erkel (2024) and classify respondents as trusting when they express trust in both the government and parliament. Respondents who express no trust in either institution are coded as having no trust. In our analysis, we use the Eurobarometer trust questions in combination with other, country-level variables (described below) to calculate a measure of trustworthiness - the key dependent variable in this study.

For the purpose of this study we merged three waves of the Eurobarometer (EB) collected during the COVID-19 pandemic: EB 94.3 (February/March 2021), EB 96.3 (July/August 2022), and EB 98.2 (January/February 2023). The EB 94.3 dataset was selected as the initial dataset because it was the first in the series to include a question on the intensity of social network usage. Conversely, EB 98.2 represents the most recent publicly available dataset at the time of this study. The final dataset, adjusted for missing values, includes approximately 64,000 respondents across 80 country-year observations. At the individual level, control variables include age, gender, education, residence size, life satisfaction, social class, left-right ideological self-placement, political sophistication, and traditional media usage.

Having constructed the types of trustworthiness as our dependent variable, we had to choose one category as the base for the multilevel multinomial regression analysis. We set skeptical trust as the reference category in our statistical model because it enables most intuitive comparisons and interpretations, as we argue that it is the most suitable benchmark for "healthy" democratic trust. Skeptical trust combines justified confidence in well-performing institutions with critical vigilance, sustaining legitimacy, cooperation, and compliance while maintaining accountability (Norris, 2011; 2024; Levi and Stoker, 2000; Marien and Hooghe, 2011). By contrast, skeptical mistrust, although also grounded in relatively accurate performance evaluations, reflects institutional underperformance and is less conducive to voluntary cooperation and political stability (van der Meer, 2010; Norris, 2011). Using skeptical trust as the base category allows us to interpret deviations, whether toward credulous trust, cynical mistrust, or skeptical mistrust, as departures from an optimal balance of confidence and scrutiny in a healthy democracy.

Social media

Social media usage is assessed using the same Eurobarometer data. Respondents are asked, "Could you tell to what extent you...? Use online social networks." The response scale comprises six points, ranging from "never" to "every day or almost every day." In addition to social media usage, the study incorporates television and printed newspaper consumption as control variables representing traditional media usage. In the findings section we compare the effects of each type of media.

In addition to the use of social media as information source, we include a measure of the related political context. Social media is increasingly leveraged for coordinated information operations (Mechkova et al. 2024). Governments, political parties and various domestic actors aim to manipulate public discourse in line with their interests, exploiting social media's vast reach and employ tactics like "troll armies" to spread targeted narratives or misinformation. Therefore, we included V-Dem's Digital

Society indicators that measure the existence and nature of these operations. We constructed so-called Social Media Disinformation index (SMDI), comprising the answers to the following three questions: How often do the government and its agents use social media to disseminate misleading viewpoints or false information to influence its own population? How often do major political parties and candidates for office use social media to disseminate misleading viewpoints or false information to influence their own population? How often do major political parties use hate speech as part of their rhetoric? (Cronbach's alpha for our index is 0.87.)

Although the survey item on hate speech does not limit the political rhetoric only on the social media environment, we decided to include it for the following reasons. First, the whole survey is focused on digital world, and the item is a part of nine-item grid, where seven out of nine statements are explicitly asking about social media environment. Therefore, it is likely that respondents had social media on mind when evaluating this item. Second, hate speech and disinformation are intertwined in its effects. Hate speech by politicians undermines rational political communication often by spreading misinformation, distorting public discourse, and impairing citizens' ability to form reasoned judgments. Democracy, as theorized by Habermas (2015), requires rational debate based on evidence and mutual respect. Hate speech deviates from this ideal by fostering exclusionary rhetoric and silencing dissent (Dryzek, 2002). Further, hate speech has been identified as one of the key mechanisms through which rational discourse is disrupted. Lewandowsky et al. (2012) demonstrate that misinformation, once internalized, is difficult to correct, shaping political attitudes through stereotypes rather than facts. Politicians exploiting hate speech manipulate emotions (Marcus et al., 2000), leading to heuristic-based, polarized judgments instead of analytical reasoning (Brader, 2005). Suhay and Erisen (2018) further show that emotionally charged rhetoric exacerbates cognitive biases, preventing citizens from evaluating policies rationally. Hate speech, therefore, is not just inflammatory rhetoric but a strategic tool that distorts political cognition. By embedding misinformation in emotional appeals, it prevents the critical reflection necessary for democratic decision-making (Somin, 2013).

In the regression models we use standard socio-demographic indicators (age, gender, education, and residence size) as control variables. In addition to these we also include self-placement on the left-right scale, as well as social class scale and political knowledge. Although Eurobarometer measures political knowledge as factual knowledge related to the EU issues, we decided to include it as a control variable as it may approximate political sophistication to some extent (Barber and Pope, 2019). Finally, we also add satisfaction with government's measures against the COVID-19 pandemic and economy evaluation as control variables in the model predicting political trust.

Macro-level data

The study evaluates government performance using macro-level indicators that capture both policy outputs and procedural quality. Policy outputs reflect the government's capacity to deliver public goods and services, such as economic growth and stability. It reflects governments' competence in managing economy, with the economic issues being among the most salient issues in European countries in long-term. Macroeconomic indicators are from Eurostat, including economic growth (per capita GDP adjusted for purchasing power), employment rates, and inflation (as measured by the Harmonized Consumers' Price Index). However, as the time of the study overlaps with the COVID-19 pandemic, we included also indicators assessing the governments' ability to manage the anti-pandemic fight. As for the COVID-19 pandemic indicators, we employed the average weekly cases and average weekly deaths. We use the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) database and calculate weekly averages for the month preceding the start of data collection.

In addition to policy performance, we also include indicators of the qualities of governments' decision-making processes, which reflect the integrity and impartiality of political institutions. Procedural performance is assessed using several indices. We use the Corruption Perception Index by Transparency International, the Liberal Democracy Index and the Rule of Law Index by the V-Dem project, which capture the transparency of governments as well as its fairness and equality for all citizens. To control for media freedom and media environment, we include the Freedom of Expression, and Alternative Sources of Information Index by V-dem (Coppedge et al. 2024), which measure government respect for press freedom and public discourse.

Macro-level indices are matched to the year preceding the Eurobarometer data collection. For example, individual-level data collected in February/March 2021 are linked to government performance indicators from 2020.

To test our hypotheses, we employed two regression models. In the first step we needed to build a statistical model that treats political trust as the dependent variable, and in addition to standard, individual level variables model includes also all relevant performance indicators on country level. The logic behind this is that if we consider the regression residuals to be a measure of deviation from rational, performance-based evaluation of political institutions, then the relevant performance needs to be captured by the model. We follow the approach of Van der Meer and Van Erkel (2023) and use multi-level binary logistic regression analysis to predict political trust. The main goal for using the first regression analysis is to get the regression residuals as a measure of deviation of the respondents' political trust level from the expected value.

Subsequently, we create four categories of trust judgment based on the residual levels. As the residuals are basically the difference between measured and expected levels in dependent variable, respondents with negative residuals display the manifested trust level lower than is the expected value based on the performance indicators. Positive residuals mean the respondents have higher values of measured trust than the expected values. Therefore, the sign of residual value indicates whether the respondent falls into category of trust or mistrust. The last issue left to decide was where to draw the line that distinguishes skeptical trust from the credulous trust, and skeptical mistrust from cynical mistrust. We decided to use the value of one standard deviation (SD) as a cut-off point. This criterion aligns with standard methodological practices in behavioral sciences, and it balances sensitivity and specificity in identifying meaningful variation (Cohen, 1988; Altman and Bland, 1995). Altman and Bland (1995) emphasize the normal distribution properties from which the 1 SD cut-off naturally arises as a marker of typical versus atypical variation. Adopting 1 SD as the cut-off thus provides a statistically grounded and interpretable metric for flagging notable deviations consistent with prior literature (Altman and Bland 1995, Montgomery 2017).

Finally, we used the created four categories of judgment on political trust as the dependent variable in the second regression model. The key predictors were the intensity of use of social media, print news and TV news, as well as the Social Media Disinformation Index, alongside standard control variables. As the dependent variable is categorical, we opted for multi-level multinomial logistic regression. We used Stata (version 17) and its generalized structural equation modeling (gsem) to fit a multinomial logistic regression with a random intercept for country-wave. This approach allows for modelling the outcome as a function of individual-level predictors while accounting for clustering and unobserved heterogeneity across country-waves by including a country-wave-specific random effect. Accordingly, the model estimates between-country variation via random effects and does not restrict analysis exclusively to within-country variation.

Results

First, we examine descriptive statistics for the key variables. Figure 1 presents a typology of political trust across European countries, distinguishing four categories: Cynical Mistrust, Skeptical Mistrust, Skeptical Trust, and Credulous Trust.

Figure 1. Types of trust in EU member states

Data sources: EB 94.3 (Spring 2021), 96.3 (Spring 2022), 98.2 (Spring 2023). Authors' calculation.

The distribution of trust types varies significantly across countries. At the upper end, countries such as Luxembourg, Finland, Denmark, and the Netherlands exhibit a higher proportion of skeptical trust, suggesting that citizens in these countries align their trust evaluations relatively closely with objective government performance. These countries also show a notable share of cynical mistrust, indicating that some citizens underestimate their government's trustworthiness despite positive performance. However, the share of credulous trust remains relatively low, meaning that overestimation of government trustworthiness is uncommon. By contrast, countries in the lower half of the graph, such as Romania, Bulgaria and Croatia, display a markedly different pattern, with an overwhelming dominance of skeptical mistrust. This suggests that citizens in these countries are similarly capable of evaluating the performance of the government, yet they are rather inclined to distrust government institutions. Therefore, it is most likely a factor based on history or culture that leads respondents (dominantly) in post-communist Europe to rather mistrust than trust the government, while having the same ability to rationally judge the performance as their counterparts in Luxembourg, Denmark or Ireland.

A key observation is that skeptical trust, which is considered the most rational and, from a certain point of view also the most democratic form of trust (Norris, 2024), is most prevalent in countries with well-functioning institutions and higher levels of governance performance, such as Luxembourg, Finland, and the Netherlands. The distribution of credulous trust is relatively small across

all countries but appears slightly more pronounced in Portugal, Cyprus, and Italy. This suggests that a subset of citizens in these contexts exhibit overconfidence in political institutions despite governance challenges, which could be attributed to partisan biases, historical trust in the state, or media influence (Norris, 2024). However, even in these countries the proportion of people with credulous trust is not much higher than in other countries.

From the perspective of democratic governance, the graph underscores the desirability of skeptical trust as the ideal balance between institutional confidence and accountability. The presence of cynical mistrust in high-performing countries suggests that some citizens remain distrustful despite good governance, while the persistence of credulous trust in certain countries highlights the risks of uncritical deference to political authority.

Table 1. Social Media Disinformation Index.

Country	2021	2022	2023
AT	-0.307	-0.306	-0.248
BE	-1.453	-1.110	-1.249
BG	0.071	-0.127	-0.134
CY	-1.051	-0.931	-0.931
CZ	-0.876	-0.860	-1.555
DE	-1.149	-1.331	-1.456
DK	-2.553	-2.553	-2.553
EE	-1.098	-1.368	-1.527
ES	-0.973	-0.961	-0.903
FI	-1.813	-1.813	-1.704
FR	-1.309	-1.063	-1.173
GR	-0.698	-0.698	-0.698
HR	-0.899	-0.883	-0.828
HU	1.221	1.165	1.212
IE	-2.184	-2.307	-2.307
IT	-0.786	-0.786	-0.786
LT	-2.429	-1.644	-1.775
LU	-1.733	-1.608	-1.608
LV	-1.790	-1.899	-1.848
MT	0.606	0.532	-0.017
NL	-1.193	-1.393	-1.352
PL	0.690	0.930	0.740
PT	-1.843	-2.019	-2.005
RO	-0.859	-0.580	-0.382
SE	-2.551	-2.386	-1.962
SI	1.233	1.533	-0.051
SK	-0.438	-0.275	-0.134

Data Source: V-Dem, Authors' calculation.

Table 1 shows the values of the Social Media Disinformation Index. The lowest score indicating the least spread of disinformation by political elite was in 2023 in Denmark (-2.553), followed by Ireland (-2.307) and Portugal (-2.005). On the other hand, the highest values were in Hungary (1.212), Poland (0.740), and Malta (-0.017). Considering all years, the lowest score was given Slovenia in 2022 (at the value 1.533). Although Denmark and Ireland belong to countries with the above-average share

of people with skeptical trust, other countries do not follow the geographical pattern we see in Figure 1. Malta, while scoring low on the Social Media Disinformation Index, has relatively high share of skeptically trusting people. Portugal is, however, scoring high in the Social Media Disinformation Index, while having relatively low share of people with skeptical trust. The SMDI thus cannot explain the country-level variation in judgment on political trust. The intensity of usage of various media as information sources is provided in Appendix 2.

What affects trustworthiness?

Based on the theoretical assumptions, we hypothesized that the social media consumption would be negatively associated with the political trustworthiness of people - the capacity to gather necessary information and employ reasoning “required for accurate judgment of political trustworthiness” (Norris 2024, p. 14). In our case, the dependent variable has four categories related to the type of trust the respondent shows towards the national government and parliament. These are Cynical Mistrust, Skeptical Mistrust, Skeptical Trust, and Credulous Trust. Arguably, the categories are distinct in terms of degree of rationality of the judgment, but they are impossible to order in terms of how much of rationality each type of trust decision requires. Therefore, we need to consider the nature of the dependent variable to be categorical. As such, the nature of the dependent variable calls for multinomial regression analysis to test the hypothesis.

Table 2. Multilevel multinomial logistic regression coefficients.

Base = Skeptical Trust	Cynical Mistrust	Skeptical Mistrust	Credulous Trust
Use of Press	0.980	0.938***	0.948***
Use of TV	0.988	0.910***	0.952**
Use of social media	0.996	1.098***	1.042***
Disinfo SM Index	1.022	1.814***	1.447*
Age	1.000	0.994***	0.995**
Gender: Women	0.932	0.769***	0.830***
Education: 16-19	1.130	1.889***	1.573***
Education: 20+	1.007	1.286**	1.140
Education: Still studying	1.090	0.823	0.940
Education: no full-time education	1.382	1.906**	1.809**
Residence: Towns/Suburbs	1.060	1.198***	1.161**
Residence: Rural areas	0.931	1.017	0.945
Social Class self-placement	0.953	0.675***	0.755***
Political Sophistication	0.937	0.710***	0.774***
Feeling informed	0.863***	0.361***	0.482***
L1[countrywave]	1.250***	2.718	2.270***
Constant	0.332	6.541***	3.886***

N = 62,985

McFadden's pseudo- R^2 = 0.4731

Notes: (1) Baseline categories: skeptical trust, men, finished education by the age of 15, cities. (2) Significance levels: *** - p-value < 0.001; ** - p-value < 0.01; * - p-value < 0.05; ^(a) - p-value < 0.1. (3) Data sources: Eurobarometer, V-Dem, Eurostat, ECD. Authors' calculations.

Table 2 shows the regression coefficients in a form of relative risk ratio for a more intuitive interpretation of the results. The results show a strong association between online information environments and probabilities of making different decisions of political mis/trust.

Frequent use of social media is significantly associated with an increased likelihood of belonging to Skeptical Mistrust, compared to Skeptical Trust. This means that individuals who engage more intensively with social media will be more likely to adopt a skeptically distrustful stance toward political institutions. The effect of the intensity of the social media use on the probability of belonging to the Credulous Trust category is also positive and statistically significant. This suggests that social media consumption pushes people away from holding a skeptical trust rather towards skeptical mistrust or credulous trust. This finding confirms the first hypothesis.

In contrast to social media, traditional media consumption (press and TV) shows consistently positive effects in terms of lowering the probability of respondent shifting away from skeptical trust category, whether to skeptical mistrust or credulous trust. This is illustrated in Figure 2, with lines showing probability of belonging to the category Skeptical Mistrust, compared to Skeptical Trust. The Y-axis shows increase/decrease of probability as the frequency of given media usage changes.

Figure 2. Effect on probability of skeptical mistrust vs. skeptical trust

Source: Eurobarometer, V-Dem, Eurostat, ECD. Authors' calculation

Both effects, the use of press and the use of TV are strongly significant. This suggests that exposure to the traditional or legacy media, such as TV news or press, increase the likelihood of making the rational, and from the quality of democracy point of view the most desired judgment of trust. Thus, we consider the third hypothesis confirmed.

The Disinformation Social Media Index has an even stronger effect than the intensity of using social media alone. Individuals in environments with a higher prevalence of disinformation on social media produced by political elites are more likely to fall into Skeptical Mistrust category (by more than

80%), and also to Credulous Trust category (by almost 45%). This suggests that higher exposure to misleading or false information contributes to the polarization of trust, leading some individuals to reject to trust the political institutions, while others adopt credulous trust. In line with our second hypothesis, this finding also aligns with broader research on the effects of digital disinformation, showing that disinformation does not simply erode trust but instead contributes to a more polarized landscape where both extreme skepticism and blind trust can emerge (Guess et al., 2020, Tappin et al., 2020, Ruggiero lo Sardo et al., 2024).

Considering individual control variables, it is worth looking closer at the impact of political sophistication. Individuals with higher political sophistication are significantly less likely to exhibit either credulous trust or skeptical mistrust, when compared to skeptical trust. This suggests that politically sophisticated individuals are more likely to make a rational judgment of trust and thus being more resistant to a generalized distrust of political institutions and actors. We also examined potential link between political sophistication and social media use. The correlation between the two is almost zero (0.08) indicating no relationship between the two.

Our findings align with established theories of political cognition, which suggest that political sophistication enhances the ability to critically process political information (Zaller, 1992; Delli Carpini and Keeter, 1996). The significant reduction in both credulous trust and skeptical mistrust among sophisticated individuals may reflect greater cognitive engagement with politics, enabling them to differentiate between legitimate concerns and unfounded trust. However, the lack of effect on cynical mistrust suggests that sophistication alone does not necessarily protect against unconditional rejection of trust in political institutions, implying that other factors - such as lack of interest in politics - may shape this orientation more strongly.

Discussion and conclusion

This study contributes to the growing body of research on political trustworthiness by examining the relationship between social media use, political elite's spread of disinformation, and the trustworthiness of political institutions. Unlike traditional studies that focus solely on political trust, our approach highlights the distinction between rational and irrational judgments of trust, underscoring the role of social media as a destabilizing factor. The findings suggest that frequent social media use is linked to a lower likelihood of individuals making rational judgments about political trust, pushing them toward skeptical mistrust. This is even more pronounced in environments where political elite uses social media to spread disinformation and political hate speech. Such polarization effect reinforces previous concerns about the role of digital platforms in distorting public perceptions of governance performance (Lorenz-Spreen et al., 2023; Majerczak and Strzelecki, 2022).

However, the social media is not the only negative influence undermining citizens' ability to judge political institutions' trustworthiness in a rational way. We consider the second major contribution of this study to be the introduction of the Disinformation Social Media Index as a measure of the extent to which political elites exploit digital platforms to spread misleading narratives. Our results indicate that exposure to high levels of disinformation (by political elite) is associated with a higher likelihood of individuals making less rational trust judgments. In countries where the Disinformation Social Media Index increases by one point the probability of belonging to the Credulous Trust category rises by more than 50%, and the probability of belonging to the Skeptical Mistrust category rises even more, by almost 90% compared to Skeptical Trust. This finding suggests that by spreading disinformation, the political elites contribute to what could be called 'trust polarization' – ability of citizens to make rational judgments on political trust.

Subsequently, this has a potential for further deterioration of democratic governance and particularly the accountability mechanisms, which assume rational judgments of voters. A well-functioning democracy relies on citizens making informed, rational evaluations of political institutions. However, our results suggest that social media use—particularly in environments saturated with disinformation—undermines this process. The algorithmic tendency to amplify sensationalist or polarizing content, and the role of political elites in spreading misleading information collectively weaken the public's ability to assess governmental trustworthiness based on objective performance criteria. Furthermore, our analysis differentiates between the effects of traditional and social media, showing that while social media exposure is linked to irrational trust judgments, traditional television and print news still has a significant positive effect in fostering rational assessments. This suggests that traditional media may still provide a counterbalance to digital misinformation.

Our results thus contribute also to the debate on the applicability of the virtuous circle thesis on social media. The virtuous circle thesis assumes that media could be a positive factor in fostering political trust and other democratic attitudes (Norris 2000). This should happen mainly because of balanced and objective information brought by traditional media to its audience, thus helping them make informed decisions. Our research shows that social media have no such effect. This could be because of the rather different mode of operation the social media have, compared to the traditional ones. Traditional media in Western societies operate under elite-driven, top-down communication frameworks tend to reinforce established democratic systems. In contrast, the unmediated, bottom-up communication dynamics of social media facilitate the circulation of alternative narratives that undermine trust in political institutions. Distinct impact of exposure to these types of media has also been shown by Ceron (2015). To improve the quality of our understanding of the impact of social media in this regard, further research would require examining different types of social media specifically. This could provide a more detailed picture, which, similar to legacy media (where we distinguish different influences, e.g. effect of public broadcaster vs. private media), could provide more accurate results.

Although the choice of data was substantially limited by the availability of survey-based data that includes items on social media use and span over a few years, the side effect is that the period covered in our analysis is that of the COVID-19 pandemic. For this reason, we included both country-level objective indicators of governments' results of the anti-pandemic measures, as well as the individual-level subjective perception of governments' measures against COVID-19.

The fact that our research covered only the so-called "pandemic" years may have influenced our findings in two ways. First, in times of crises and uncertainty people are in higher demand for information. During the pandemic the rules impacting daily life changed rather frequently (closing and opening schools, border crossing, etc.). Many people were forced to change (not only) work routines and were thus in need of information on how to function during the pandemic. Internet, and social media particularly might have served as an important information source, with many people left dependent on on-line tools for other aspects of life anyway. Second, there is a consensus that the spread of disinformation and fake news on social media was much more intense during the pandemic than during the previous crises (Khan, Mikhalas, and Akuzada 2021), deserving also labels as infodemic (Tangcharoensathien et al. 2020). The combination of the two factors may contribute to citizens' inability of evaluating the governments' performance objectively and translate it into a rational judgment of political trust. Future research could also focus on the potential impact of social media use on political trustworthiness in politically more stable and quiet times without multiple external crises layering up.

A potential limitation of this study lies in the choice of one standard deviation (1 SD) as the cutoff point to define when the deviation of the measured trust level from the expected trust is “too large.” While 1 SD is a widely used and statistically justified threshold reflecting the range within which approximately 68% of normally distributed data falls, it remains an arbitrary convention rather than a universally optimal or context-specific boundary. The reliance on a fixed cut-off like ± 1 SD carries the risk of misclassification or over-simplification. However, we also performed a sensitivity analysis. We ran the same regression models with two alternatives, the cut-off points set as a) three quarters of a standard deviation, and b) one and a quarter of standard deviation. In both cases the hypothesized relationships proved to be the same.

One of the challenges to future research is examining the role of media literacy in shaping political trust judgments. If citizens can be equipped with the skills to critically assess online information, they may be better positioned to resist the distortions caused by algorithmic curation or spread of disinformation. Our findings also showed that political knowledge is contributing to the likelihood of remaining in the category of Skeptical Trust.

Also, future research could examine the long-term consequences of the patterns identified in this study. If disinformation- and social media-driven polarization in trust judgments persists over time, it may have lasting implications for political participation, electoral behavior, and institutional legitimacy. Longitudinal studies tracking changes in trustworthiness evaluations across multiple election cycles would provide valuable insights into the stability of these effects.

This study provides empirical evidence that social media use, particularly in environments where political elites spread disinformation, significantly undermines citizens’ ability to make rational judgments about political trustworthiness. By shifting the focus from trust to trustworthiness, we offer an understanding of how digital media distort democratic accountability. The findings have critical implications for media policy, political communication, and efforts to safeguard democratic institutions from the destabilizing effects of digital disinformation. Addressing these challenges will require coordinated efforts from policymakers, media organizations, and civil society to ensure that the digital public sphere supports rather than undermines informed democratic engagement.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon research and innovation program under the research project TRUEDEM ‘Trust in European Democracies’ grant no. 101095237 and the EU NextGenerationEU through the Recovery and Resilience Plan for Slovakia under the project No. 09I01-03-V04-00023.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Gesis archive at <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14081>, <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13908>, and <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14076>. This study also uses data from V-Dem institute available at <https://doi.org/10.23696/mcwt-fr58>, data from European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control available at <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/data-daily-new-cases-covid-19-eueea-country>, and data on economic development from Eurostat available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database>.

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Appendix 1 – Multilevel regression analysis for estimating trust residuals

In line with the methodology outlined by Van der Meer and Van Erkel (2023) and Norris (2024), we operationalized trustworthiness as the residual error in multilevel logistic regression model. The model assesses the extent to which governance performance indices predict observed levels of public trust across country-years. Trustworthiness is measured by linking country-year estimates of governmental trust from the Eurobarometer with selected governance performance indices. These indices encompass policy outputs (e.g., levels of economic development), pandemic-specific indicators (e.g., infection and mortality rates), and procedural quality metrics (e.g., governance quality). Trustworthiness is calculated as the residual error in models predicting observed trust levels based on these indicators.

Similarly, as in Van der Meer and Van Erkel (2023), our measure of political trust relies on two dichotomous indicators: “Do you tend to trust or not trust the national government?” and “Do you tend to trust or not trust the national parliament?” Respondents are classified as trusting only if they express trust in both institutions. A lack of trust in either institution is coded as mistrust.

The right-hand side of the equation consisted of basic socio-demographic variables as gender, age, education, size of residence, left-right and liberal-conservative self-placement. On the country level, we used several objectively measured indicators that capture both policy outputs and procedural quality. Policy outputs capture governments’ capacity to provide public goods, particularly economic stability and growth—issues long central in Europe. We use Eurostat macroeconomic indicators (per capita GDP adjusted for purchasing power, employment, inflation via HICP). Because our study coincides with the COVID-19 pandemic, we also include governments’ crisis management capacity, measured by average weekly cases and deaths from the ECDC (calculated for the month before data collection). Beyond performance, we assess the quality of decision-making, reflecting institutional integrity and impartiality. For this, we use Transparency International’s CPI, V-Dem’s Liberal Democracy and Rule of Law indices, and its Freedom of Expression and Alternative Sources of Information index (Coppedge et al. 2024), capturing transparency, fairness, and media freedom.

Table A.1 presents the results of a multilevel logistic regression predicting political trust. Coefficients are reported as odds ratios, with standard errors in parentheses and significance indicated by asterisks. Age is positively associated with trust, with each additional year of age increases the odds of trusting political institutions by 0.7%. Gender also matters, with women reporting higher levels of trust than men corresponding to a 5.6% increase in the odds of trust. Education displays a complex pattern. Respondents with 16–19 years of education have odds of trust that are about 19% lower than those with 15 years or fewer. By contrast, individuals still enrolled in education report 29% higher odds of trust. Those without any full-time education are 18% less likely to trust. These results suggest that both higher education at certain levels and exclusion from education are associated with reduced trust, while ongoing educational involvement strengthens trust. Residential location has a modest but significant effect. Compared to people living in cities, respondents from towns or suburbs show 8% lower odds of political trust. Rural residence does not significantly differ from urban areas. Self-placement on the left–right ideological scale is unrelated to trust. Subjective social class, however, is strongly predictive. Each step upward in self-assessed class increases the odds of trust by 21.8%.

As for the country level predictors, the macroeconomic performance demonstrates clear associations. Higher GDP per capita (adjusted for purchasing power) is positively related to trust. Each additional 1,000 euros in GDP per capita translates into approximately a 5% increase in the odds of trust. Inflation is negatively associated with trust, a one-point increase in the harmonized consumer price index reduces the odds of trust by 2.5%. Employment rates do not significantly predict trust.

COVID-19 dynamics at the country level do not show direct effects. Neither average weekly cases nor weekly deaths per million inhabitants are significantly associated with trust, suggesting that short-term epidemiological indicators were not decisive for citizens' trust during the studied period.

Table A1. Multilevel logistic regression predicting trust.

Variable	Coefficient
Age	0.007*** (0.001)
Gender: Woman	0.054* (0.030)
Education: 16-19	-0.214*** (0.064)
Education: 20+	0.013 (0.067)
Education: Still studying	0.252*** (0.090)
Education: no full-time education	-0.205 (0.136)
Residence: Towns/suburbs	-0.082** (0.037)
Residence: Rural	-0.026 (0.042)
Left – Right placement	0.035 (0.031)
Social class, self assessment	0.218*** (0.025)
Weekly cases (Covid, per 1 million inhab.)	-0.000 (0.000)
Weekly deaths (Covid, per 1 million inhab.)	-0.005 (0.004)
GDP	0.005*** (0.001)
Inflation rate	-0.025* (0.014)
Employment rate	0.019 (0.015)
Rule of law index	-2.734* (1.476)
Liberal democracy index	1.021 (1.849)
Freedom of expression and alternative information sources index	-0.831 (1.682)
Corruption Perception index	0.027*** (0.010)
Constant	-2.769** (1.149)
var(_cons[countrywave])	0.202*** (0.054)
Observations	65,544

Notes: (1) Baseline categories: skeptical trust, men, finished education by the age of 15, cities. (2) Significance levels: *** - p-value < 0.01; ** - p-value < 0.05; * - p-value < 0.10. (3) Data sources: Eurobarometer, V-Dem, Eurostat, ECD. Authors' calculations.

Most institutional quality indicators are not significantly related to trust. The Rule of Law Index and the Liberal Democracy Index, as well as the Freedom of Expression and Alternative Sources of Information Index, yield insignificant results. The only exception is the Corruption Perceptions Index, which shows a marginally significant positive effect (OR = 1.023, $p < 0.10$). Substantively, a one-point increase on this index corresponds to a 2.3% rise in the odds of trust. Although the effect is relatively small, it suggests that perceptions of lower corruption may bolster institutional trust.

The results from this regression analysis suggest that trust in political institutions is shaped by a combination of socio-demographic and macro-economic factors, with institutional quality playing a more limited role. Among individual-level variables, age, gender, educational experience, and subjective social class emerge as consistent predictors. At the macro level, economic conditions—particularly GDP growth and inflation—exert stronger and more systematic effects on trust than institutional quality indicators. Pandemic-related mortality and morbidity do not appear to have shaped trust directly during the observed period. These results indicate that citizens' trust is grounded more firmly in tangible socio-economic realities.

Appendix 2 – Intensity of use of various media as information source (2023)

Table A2. Use of press (%).

Country	never	less often	2-3 times a month	once a week	2-3 times a week	every day
AT	12.88	8.47	8.21	15.70	16.80	37.94
BE	22.86	13.15	9.88	13.85	12.43	27.83
BG	38.17	18.38	11.91	15.51	9.74	6.28
CY	46.01	11.88	7.39	8.79	9.69	16.24
CZ	26.02	23.83	9.33	16.85	15.17	8.81
DE	19.52	17.29	5.80	11.29	17.24	28.86
DK	34.32	10.98	6.57	6.94	9.77	31.42
EE	17.12	18.62	10.23	17.91	17.44	18.67
ES	42.05	15.7	5.64	11.92	12.67	12.02
FI	8.74	9.74	7.75	13.72	13.24	46.81
FR	42.48	9.73	5.25	13.11	12.35	17.07
GR	39.94	28.98	7.63	11.60	6.92	4.92
HR	21.72	23.46	8.71	14.95	13.10	18.06
HU	41.03	12.62	10.83	12.41	10.80	12.32
IE	23.98	12.43	6.59	13.64	23.02	20.34
IT	31.55	12.84	10.05	16.89	15.78	12.90
LT	47.51	8.53	6.46	13.40	15.27	8.83
LU	17.26	10.92	3.97	8.35	16.77	42.74
LV	30.37	13.41	8.84	14.66	15.87	16.85
MT	44.61	6.66	6.12	7.07	7.32	28.21
NL	22.24	8.52	4.42	9.96	11.66	43.20
PL	36.39	18.41	14.25	15.02	11.42	4.49
PT	31.93	16.02	8.16	21.23	12.03	10.63
RO	49.93	10.34	9.89	16.10	9.50	4.23
SE	10.11	12.27	9.00	10.16	13.78	44.67
SI	26.88	16.8	10.00	17.62	11.39	17.30
SK	25.73	16.76	8.48	18.91	14.37	15.76
Total	29.57	14.65	8.31	13.88	13.30	20.29

Data source: EB 98.2 (Spring 2023)

Table A3. Use of TV (%).

Country	never	less often	2-3 times a month	once a week	2-3 times a week	every day
AT	2.52	1.86	0.80	3.80	14.50	76.53
BE	3.77	3.41	1.39	5.30	15.69	70.44
BG	0.44	1.31	0.56	1.40	6.13	90.16
CY	3.81	5.00	1.09	1.07	8.66	80.37
CZ	7.26	5.32	1.51	3.45	12.45	70.00
DE	8.13	5.05	1.35	4.52	11.01	69.94
DK	11.53	4.91	3.82	6.12	13.62	60.00
EE	9.71	6.11	2.34	5.84	12.62	63.38
ES	6.92	6.17	1.22	3.56	8.86	73.25
FI	7.57	7.90	4.30	5.74	11.95	62.54

FR	11.85	4.09	1.52	3.28	10.57	68.68
GR	1.17	2.27	1.07	3.34	8.79	83.37
HR	1.39	1.17	1.26	2.95	6.97	86.26
HU	4.57	3.13	2.22	3.57	12.43	74.07
IE	3.42	3.00	1.09	3.68	11.69	77.12
IT	1.06	0.76	0.81	2.21	9.07	86.10
LT	8.07	3.20	1.84	5.50	12.64	68.75
LU	10.68	8.17	2.11	5.13	15.49	58.42
LV	11.63	6.81	2.32	4.19	9.42	65.62
MT	7.40	1.94	0.99	6.49	14.77	68.40
NL	12.59	4.66	2.40	6.05	12.24	62.06
PL	1.68	1.21	0.31	2.43	12.77	81.60
PT	1.38	0.56	0.51	1.51	5.66	90.38
RO	2.13	0.25	0.60	1.70	7.97	87.35
SE	12.38	6.74	5.22	5.28	10.42	59.96
SI	6.62	7.84	2.68	8.03	13.90	60.92
SK	4.88	3.35	3.10	4.90	13.00	70.77
Total	6.01	3.85	1.81	4.10	11.11	73.13

Data source: EB 98.2 (Spring 2023)

Table A4. Use of social media (%).

Country	never	less often	2-3 times a month	once a week	2-3 times a week	every day
AT	21.83	5.39	3.76	8.66	15.45	44.91
BE	16.52	4.41	1.81	7.99	17.46	51.82
BG	19.62	0.91	1.31	3.24	14.35	60.58
CY	16.8	2.11	1.12	2.96	11.60	65.40
CZ	22.35	7.14	2.16	4.64	12.78	50.93
DE	29.02	7.37	4.10	5.94	17.02	36.55
DK	9.75	2.89	2.44	3.30	11.20	70.42
EE	17.49	3.83	2.50	5.27	12.90	58.00
ES	25.31	2.44	1.75	3.98	12.65	53.87
FI	17.01	3.37	2.99	3.80	10.41	62.42
FR	35.56	4.17	1.03	4.73	10.93	43.58
GR	25.62	2.21	0.46	2.33	8.37	61.01
HR	17.97	2.40	1.56	7.11	10.39	60.57
HU	22.43	2.58	1.51	5.67	10.77	57.03
IE	17.80	4.30	1.64	3.45	20.48	52.34
IT	24.33	3.11	1.95	8.27	17.23	45.11
LT	22.09	0.68	0.08	2.29	8.83	66.03
LU	18.66	7.44	2.25	6.64	14.69	50.32
LV	19.41	2.89	1.93	5.04	9.33	61.41
MT	11.31	1.23	0.58	0.40	15.66	70.82
NL	15.74	6.91	1.86	5.19	11.20	59.10
PL	20.57	3.61	2.57	6.37	19.77	47.10
PT	26.15	1.40	1.08	5.75	10.43	55.18
RO	25.81	1.17	2.55	4.75	11.61	54.11
SE	9.54	4.15	1.45	4.85	8.24	71.76

Country	never	less often	2-3 times a month	once a week	2-3 times a week	every day
SI	25.56	4.67	2.50	5.54	12.64	49.10
SK	22.75	2.54	1.60	3.66	13.34	56.11
Total	21.06	3.59	1.94	5.00	12.96	55.46

Data source: EB 98.2 (Spring 2023)

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